

Brief Reports

Emotional intelligence and emotional reactivity: Understanding the hypersensitivity hypothesis

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ABSTRACT

The hypersensitivity hypothesis suggests that individuals with high emotional intelligence (EI) experience emotions more intensely than those with lower EI. The aim of the current study was to examine whether high-EI individuals perceive and experience stronger affective responses in response to the emotions observed in others. To investigate this, participants were asked to evaluate the intensity and arousal of facial expressions displaying anger, happiness, and neutrality. The three facets of ability EI were measured: recognition, understanding and management of emotion. It was hypothesized that individuals with high EI would report greater intensity and arousal in response to angry and happy expressions compared to neutral ones. Results confirm the hypersensitivity hypothesis regarding the intensity of emotions, although findings were less consistent for arousal. Furthermore, findings varied across different facets of emotional intelligence (EI): individuals with greater emotion understanding and perception evaluated angry expressions more extremely, while those higher on emotion management emphasized happiness more. These results suggest that individuals with high EI tend to experience and evaluate emotions more extremely, particularly in terms of intensity, and show that the link between EI and emotional reactivity varies based on the specific emotion involved and the particular EI facet being examined. Particularly interesting was that evaluations of intensity of *happy* expressions were more amplified than evaluations of *angry* expressions in high EI individuals.

1. Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) is a multifaceted construct encompassing the ability to recognize, understand, regulate, and express emotions, as well as the capacity to manage interpersonal relationships effectively. Initially introduced by psychologists Peter Salovey and John Mayer in the early 1990s, EI gained significant attention due to its perceived importance in personal and professional success. Unlike traditional intelligence measures focusing solely on cognitive abilities, EI emphasizes the critical role of emotions in human functioning. Recent studies have continued to explore and refine the understanding of emotional intelligence as an ability, shedding light on its underlying mechanisms, assessment methods, and practical implications.

One significant development pertains to introducing emotion-information processing as a new component of EI. The fundamental idea is that Emotional Intelligence (EI) can be understood as comprising two interconnected yet distinct elements: 1) Emotion Knowledge (EI_K), which encompasses acquired and culturally influenced knowledge about

emotions, typically assessed through current ability EI tests; and 2) Emotion Information Processing (EI_P), assessed through emotion information processing tasks, which pertains to how individuals process emotions and emotion-related information. EI_P demands quicker processing compared to EI_K and relies on bottom-up responses to emotional stimuli (Fiori et al., 2022). Although both EI components contribute to the same underlying EI factor, they are anticipated to predict different aspects of emotionally intelligent behavior: more intuitive (system 1) emotional responses for EI_P and more deliberative (system 2) emotional responses for EI_K (see also Fiori, 2009; Fiori & Vesely-Maillefer, 2019).

This revised understanding of EI suggests that individuals high in EI_P display heightened sensitivity to emotions and emotion-related information, reflected in more extreme scores on emotional tasks. Such proposition has been linked to the 'hypersensitivity hypothesis', for which individuals high in EI are more sensitive to emotion and emotion information than their low-EI counterparts (Fiori & Ortony, 2021). The hypersensitivity hypothesis has been eventually refined to identify the emotion-processing steps possibly involved in hypersensitive reactions

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Table 1
Descriptives and correlations of the variables in the study.

	M (SD)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Age	29 (9.8)										
2. Gender	1.7 (0.5)	0.12									
3. STEU	0.6 (0.1)	-0.04	0.14								
4. STEM	0.6 (0.1)	0.01	0.09	0.29***							
5. GERT	24.4 (6.2)	-0.1	0.12	0.58***	0.40***						
6. Int Neu	2.9 (1.3)	0.25**	-0.07	-0.21**	-0.13	-0.42***					
7. Int Ha	6.3 (1.7)	0.05	0	0.1	0.09	0.21**	-0.12				
8. Int An	7.2 (1.1)	0.12	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.24**	0.32***			
9. Ar Neu	2.3 (1.0)	0.23**	-0.06	-0.25**	-0.16*	-0.31***	0.52***	0.05	0.09		
10. Ar Ha	5.7 (1.9)	0.22**	0.04	-0.16*	-0.02	-0.17*	0.30***	0.27***	0.38***	0.34***	
11. Ar An	5.1 (1.9)	0.16*	-0.04	0.05	-0.05	0.14	-0.07	0.26**	0.30***	0.23**	0.50***

Note. STEU: Situational Test of Emotion Understanding, STEM: Situational Test of Emotion Management, GERT: Geneva Emotion Recognition Test, Int: Intensity, Ar: Arousal, Neu: Neutral, Ha: Happy, An: Angry.

* $p < .05$

** $p < .01$

*** $p < .0001$.

of high EI individuals (Fiori et al., 2023). Evidence has been provided that high EI individuals are hypersensitive with respect to stronger attention to emotional vs. neutral stimuli (Nicolet-dit-Félix et al., 2023), and stronger accuracy in detecting complex emotion blends in facial expressions (Gillioz et al., 2023).

The goal of the current investigation was to test another important cornerstone of the hypersensitivity hypothesis, namely whether high EI individuals evaluate emotional stimuli, such as emotional expressions, as more intense and if they experience stronger affective reactions in response to the emotions perceived in others. To this purpose, we employed two distinct dimensions to describe the nature of emotional experiences: emotional *intensity*, which refers to the perception of the magnitude or strength of an emotional stimulus, such as an emotional picture; and emotional *arousal*, which pertains to the activation or strength of the response experienced in oneself in relation to the emotional stimulus (Goeleven et al., 2008). We asked participants to rate the intensity and arousal of angry, happy and neutral facial expressions. Positive and negative expressions were chosen on purpose, to test whether hypersensitivity may apply to both positive and negative emotions and emotional reactions. We expected that emotional stimuli would be rated as more intense and more arousing than neutral ones, and that the difference between emotional and neutral stimuli would be larger for high- compared to low-EI individuals. The comparison with neutral stimuli was necessary to determine whether EI is associated with hypersensitivity to *emotional* stimuli, as compared to a generalized tendency to give higher intensity/arousal ratings, regardless of the emotional nature of stimuli. High EI individuals would show more differences in their intensity ratings of happy (Hypothesis 1a) and angry expressions (Hypothesis 1b) compared to neutral expressions. High EI individuals would also show more differences in their arousal ratings of happy (Hypothesis 2a) and angry expressions (Hypothesis 2b) compared to neutral expressions. We measured three facets of ability EI: recognition, understanding, and management of emotion.

2. Method

2.1. General procedure and participants

This study was part of a greater project investigating the relationship between hypersensitivity to emotion and EI. The study was conducted in two sessions: (1) a battery of questionnaires and (2) the evaluation task presented in this paper as well as other tasks not reported here (see Gillioz et al., 2023; Nicolet-dit-Félix et al., 2023).

English-speaking adults were recruited online (approval rate above 95 %) on the platform Prolific (www.prolific.co). Two-hundred and three individuals completed both parts of the study. Participants who did not answer correctly to at least two out of three attentional checks

and those with less than four correct responses in the emotion recognition EI test were removed. Our final sample consisted in 155 participants (52 men), aged between 18 and 63 ($M = 29.02$, $SD = 9.81$). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the ethical committee of the University of Geneva. All participants gave their informed consent. They were paid £7.5 per hour.

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. The Geneva emotion recognition test short version (GERT-S) (Schlegel & Scherer, 2016)

The GERT-S is a test with 42 clips where professional actors perform 14 emotions using facial, vocal, and body cues. Participants identify the emotions, receiving scores for accuracy. Cronbach's alpha was 0.79 in our sample.

2.2.2. The situational test of emotional understanding-brief (STEU-B) (Allen et al., 2014)

The STEU-B assesses emotion comprehension through 19 items, asking participants to identify emotions in scenarios. Responses are evaluated as correct or incorrect. It focuses on understanding protagonists' feelings, with a test-retest reliability of 0.72 (Libbrecht & Lievens, 2012).

2.2.3. The situational test of emotional management-brief (STEM-B) (Allen et al., 2015)

The STEM-B is 18-item test measuring respondents' strategies for emotion and situation management. It requires selecting effective actions based on scenarios, with answers judged by expert consensus. Test-retest reliability has been reported at 0.85 (Libbrecht & Lievens, 2012).

2.3. Materials and rating task

The materials consisted in 64 faces from the Karolinska Directed Emotional Faces (KDEF) database, series A (Lundqvist et al., 1998). Thirty-two images displayed a neutral expression, 16 a happy expression and 16 an angry expression. The emotional faces had similar ratings of intensity and arousal (Goeleven et al., 2008): angry: $M_{int} = 6.7$, $SD_{int} = 0.6$, $Mar = 4.1$, $SD_{ar} = 0.6$; happy: $M_{int} = 6.9$, $SD_{int} = 0.3$, $Mar = 4.1$, $SD_{ar} = 0.3$; neutral: $M_{int} = 4.7$, $SD_{int} = 0.4$, $Mar = 2.6$, $SD_{ar} = 0.3$. We cropped all stimuli into a standard oval shape (346×460 pixels), hair and external features were removed, and the eyes were aligned at the same height (see example in Supplemental material).

First, in the intensity rating task, participants saw all faces, one at a time, and were asked to report the intensity of the expressed feeling on a scale ranging from 1 = not at all to 9 = completely. Then, in the arousal rating task, participants saw all faces again and reported the extent to

Fig. 1. Interaction effects between EI facets and emotional valence of the faces on intensity ratings. A: Emotion understanding, B: Emotion management, C: Emotion recognition.

which each face elicited an affective response in themselves, using a self-assessment manikin with 9 choices from calm to excited (Bradley & Lang, 1994). The order of the tasks was the same for all participants; the order of the stimuli was randomized in each task.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 displays descriptive statistics and correlations of the study variables. All EI facets were correlated with each other. Regarding neutral stimuli, STEU and GERT were negatively correlated to intensity ratings and all EI facets were negatively correlated to arousal ratings. Regarding emotional stimuli, GERT was correlated to intensity ratings of happy faces and STEU and GERT were negatively correlated to arousal ratings of happy faces. Ratings of intensity of angry expressions obtained the highest score ($M = 7.2, SD = 1.1$), whereas ratings of arousal of neutral expressions obtained the lowest ($M = 2.3; SD = 1.0$).

Table 2
Simple effects of EI facets on intensity ratings for the different modalities of emotion.

	Happy			Angry			Neutral		
	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>
STEU	0.18	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.64	-0.27	0.07	< 0.001
STEM	0.16	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.74	-0.17	0.07	0.02
GERT	0.38	0.08	<0.001	0.07	0.08	0.4	-0.53	0.07	< 0.001

Note. STEU: Situational Test of Emotion Understanding, STEM: Situational Test of Emotion Management, GERT: Geneva Emotion Recognition Test.

3.2. Data analysis

As our data come from repeated measures, the evaluations of intensity and arousal were analyzed with linear mixed models in R (R Core Team, 2021). We fitted models for each ability-EI facet independently. Each model included age and gender as control variables, and a random intercept for participant. We tested our hypotheses with fixed effects of emotion (neutral vs. happy vs. angry) and EI facet and their interaction. As we had specific hypotheses related to the difference between neutral and angry/happy stimuli, emotion was treatment coded with the reference level set to neutral. All continuous variables were standardized. Full results are available in Supplemental Materials.

3.3. Intensity ratings

As shown on Fig. 1, the difference in intensity ratings between happy and neutral faces was larger at high levels of EI compared to low levels of EI, as shown by a significant EI facet x emotion-happy interaction in all models (STEU: $\beta = 0.45, 95\%CI [0.37-0.53], p < .001$; STEM: $\beta = 0.33, 95\%CI [0.25-0.41], p < .001$, GERT: $\beta = 0.91, 95\%CI [0.84-0.99], p <$

Table 3
Simple effects of EI facets on arousal ratings for the different modalities of emotion.

	Happy			Angry			Neutral		
	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>
STEU	-0.29	0.09	0.002	0.11	0.09	0.23	-0.23	0.09	0.008
STEM	-0.03	0.09	0.76	-0.1	0.09	0.26	-0.17	0.09	0.06
GERT	-0.28	0.09	0.002	0.3	0.09	0.001	-0.28	0.09	0.001

Note. STEU: Situational Test of Emotion Understanding, STEM: Situational Test of Emotion Management, GERT: Geneva Emotion Recognition Test.

Fig. 2. Interaction effects between EI facets and emotional valence of the faces on arousal ratings. A: Emotion understanding, B: Emotion management, C: Emotion recognition.

.001). This interaction effect was driven by an increase in intensity ratings of happy faces and a decrease in intensity ratings of neutral faces depending on ability-EI (see Table 2 for simple slopes results), supporting Hypothesis 1a. There was also a significant interaction effect between EI and emotion-angry for all ability-EI facets (STEU: $\beta = 0.31$, 95%CI [0.23–0.39], $p < .001$; STEM: $\beta = 0.19$, 95%CI [0.11–0.27], $p < .001$, GERT: $\beta = 0.60$, 95%CI [0.52–0.67], $p < .001$). This interaction effect was characterized by a decrease in intensity ratings of neutral faces associated to EI. The difference in intensity ratings between angry and neutral faces was still larger at higher levels of ability-EI than at low levels, supporting Hypothesis 1b.

3.4. Arousal ratings

The results related to arousal differed depending on the ability-EI facet and the emotion considered. Regarding emotion understanding and emotion perception, there was a significant interaction involving emotion-angry (STEU: $\beta = 0.34$, 95%CI [0.26–0.42], $p < .001$; GERT: $\beta = 0.58$, 95%CI [0.50–0.66], $p < .001$), with the difference in arousal

ratings between angry and neutral faces becoming larger at higher levels of ability-EI than at low levels (see Table 3 for simple slopes results).

For emotion management, we observed a different trend. The significant interaction was related to emotion-happy ($\beta = 0.14$, 95%CI [0.06–0.22], $p = .001$): as emotion management increased, the difference in arousal ratings between happy and neutral faces became larger (see Fig. 2).

Hypotheses 2a and 2b were consequently only partially confirmed.

4. Discussion

Our results describe a more complex picture than the one hypothesized. First, evaluations of intensity of happy expressions were more amplified than evaluations of angry expressions in high EI individuals. While we acknowledge high average ratings of intensity of angry expressions, which might have rendered difficult to detect individual differences, the finding about happy expressions is worthwhile and might point to one of the possible mechanisms explaining the association between EI and thriving. High EI individuals might have higher levels of

wellbeing because they tend to amplify the intensity of positive facial expressions, making social interaction easier and more pleasant (see also Schlegel, 2020).

Second, while hypotheses about hypersensitivity were generally confirmed with respect to intensity of emotions, results were less consistent for arousal. The most interesting (and unexpected) finding was that the results depended on the EI facet: whereas participants higher as compared to lower in emotion understanding and emotion perception had more extreme evaluations of angry expressions, participants higher on emotion management amplified happy expressions. It might well be the case that emotion management involves accentuating positive emotional reactions, such as responses to happy expressions, as an emotion regulation strategy. Third, results point to a bipolarity of evaluations of emotional vs. neutral expressions, a phenomenon also observed in the context of other types of evaluations, such as words, faces, job satisfaction (Robinson et al., 2023), and impressions of others (Fiori & Ortony, 2021) for which positive and negative evaluations provided by high EI individuals are strongly and inversely related to each other.

We observed an unexpected ceiling effect of ratings of intensity of angry expressions, which might have prevented individual differences in EI to emerge. Despite having selected angry expressions based on a level of intensity and arousal comparable to that of happy faces, participants found that anger expressions were on average more intense. We believe a possible explanation resides in the contrast perceived between angry vs. neutral and happy expressions. The primacy of anger with respect to other emotions is known in the literature and is often understood in terms of the evolutionary advantage of anger detection.

In future studies it would be preferable to choose several and more nuanced categories of emotions to avoid that one type of positive expression (happiness) is contrasted to one type of negative expression (anger). Future research on hypersensitivity in relation to EI might benefit from including measures of trait EI, which captures different aspects of EI and whose characterization, based on self-reports, might reveal a different way of functioning of hypersensitivity in high EI individuals.

Overall, results support the hypersensitivity hypothesis that more extreme emotional reactions, especially with respect to emotional intensity, characterize the way of functioning of high EI individuals. Further research is needed to understand how this form of hypersensitivity may lead to the positive outcomes well documented in the literature.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marina Fiori: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Christelle Gillioz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maroussia Nicolet-dit-Félix:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declarations of interest

None.

Data availability

The data and analyses code are available online at <https://osf.io/q4fxc/>.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2024.112792>.

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